

METHODS OF DEVELOPING LANGUAGE COMPETENCES OF B1 LEVEL
STUDENTS BASED ON A PERSON-ORIENTED APPROACH

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ELSEVIER

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Abstract: In this article, the author comprehensively covered and summarized the results of the empirical research conducted on methods of developing the language competences of B1 level students based on a person-oriented approach. Also, he gave examples of the most effective innovative methods in the process of teaching a foreign language

Keywords: person-oriented approach, paradigm, education, skills, methodology, ability, language barriers

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Abstract: Ushbu maqolada muallif B1 darajadagi o'quvchilarning til kompetentsiyalarini shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv asosida rivojlantirish usullari bo'yicha olib borgan imperik tadqiqot natijalarini keng yoritgan hamda xulosalagan. Shuningdek, chet tili o'qitish jarayonida eng samarador bo'lgan inno shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv, paradigma, ta'lim, ko'nikmalar, metodologiya, qobiliyat, til to'siqlarivatsion metodlardan namunalar keltirgan

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Abstract: В данной статье автор всесторонне осветил и обобщил результаты проведенного эмпирического исследования методов развития языковых компетенций учащихся уровня B1 на основе лично-ориентированного подхода. Также он привел примеры наиболее эффективных инновационных методов в процессе обучения иностранному языку.

Keywords: лично-ориентированный подход, парадигма, образование, навыки, методология, способность, языковой барьер.

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Introduction The development of a post-industrial society in which information becomes the main object of human activity, the proclamation of the principles of humanization and democratization in society have changed the values of society and the paradigm of education. According to the requirements of the time, today a free, developed and educated person is valued, capable of creating in a constantly changing world. Which, in turn, requires the full development of the personality and its communicative abilities, allowing it to enter the world community and function successfully in it. The modern school is aimed at developing the student's personality, his cognitive and creative abilities, independence, and the desire for continuing education. "A graduate of the school,"

emphasizes I.L. Bim, "must have the necessary knowledge that makes up a holistic picture of the world, skills and abilities to carry out various types of activities, must possess modern personality-oriented learning technologies, experience in creative activity and be ready for interpersonal and intercultural cooperation within his country and on the international-native level" [1]. The living conditions of a person have changed-the requirements for the level and quality of a specialist's proficiency in a foreign language have changed. The requirements for the quality of education have increased in the light of decisions The Bologna Process - the importance of knowledge, proficiency in a foreign language and the ability to practically use it has increased. In the labor market in the conditions of a market economy, yesterday's school graduate offers "his main personal capital - competence" as a gift linguistic professional communicative competence, professionalism, qualification. "The higher the level of qualification, the more freedom of choice he will have in the labor market, the more he will be in demand in life" [2]. With the transition of education to a new paradigm of "education through life" and a personality-oriented approach as the main strategy of education, the goals of education are realized during the formation of competencies. The evaluation of the result of education is focused on the concepts of "com- competence" and "competence" of students within the framework of the competence approach in education. "The competence approach is aimed at developing the personal qualities of students and involves a significant strengthening of the practical orientation of education" [3]. "Competence is the possession, possession by a student of the corresponding competence, including a personal attitude to it and to the activity. Competence is an already established personality quality, or a combination of the qualities of a student. This is the minimum experience of activity in a given field" [4]. The concept of competence includes cognitive, operational and technological, motivational, ethical, social and behavioral components. The concept of competence includes learning outcomes, i.e. knowledge and skills, a system of value orientations, habits [5]. The competence approach correlates with the personality-oriented approach and contributes to its implementation. The analysis of the state standards of secondary (full) general education in a foreign language at the basic and profile levels showed that in the general requirements for the education of a graduate of a profile school-personality parameters related to key competencies are laid down. "Competence is a predetermined, social requirement (norm) for mandatory training of a student, necessary for his effective productive activity in a certain field" [6]. "A comprehensive school," it is noted in the Concept of Modernization of Russian Education, "should form a new system of universal knowledge, skills and abilities, as well as the experience of independent activity and personal responsibility of

students, that is, modern key competencies" [7]. The term "competence" represents the highest level of control over the ways of developing professional activity.

Methods The concept of "competence" is included in the conceptual apparatus of the theory and methodology of teaching foreign languages. Back in the 60s of the last century, H. Chomsky introduced the concept of "competence" to denote an integrative learning goal. He supplemented the concept of "Linguistic competence" with the concept of "communicative competence". Modern key competencies of foreign language communication are a new system of universal knowledge, skills, skills, as well as the experience of independent activity and personal responsibility of students. What should be the system of universal knowledge? What skills and the skills you need to master? What content should education be filled with? What should be the structure of education in the senior classes of a specialized school? The content and structure of any object are determined by its main functions of the senior level of general secondary education. Regarding a foreign language, we can say that the main functions of foreign language (language) education are laid down in its purpose:

- to ensure the completion of the language general education training of school graduates;

- to help high school students in their self-determination and in determining the role of a foreign language in their future plans for the future;

- to create a base for the possible use of a foreign language in work after graduation;

- to target and prepare high school students to continue language vocational education, where a foreign language can be the goal of professional activity or a means to acquire another subject area [8].

There are several approaches to classifying the key competencies of a graduate of a specialized school. I.L. Bim identifies the following.

Six key competencies of A.V. Barannikov:

1. educational competencies;
2. research competencies;
3. social and personal;
4. communication competencies;
5. competencies in the field of organizational activity and cooperation;
6. personality-adaptive competencies [9].

Seven key competencies of A.V. Khutorsky, based on:

1. The main goals of general secondary education,
2. on the structural representation of social experience and personal experience
3. on the main activities of the student, allowing him to gain experience, life skills and practical activities in modern

society:

- value-semantic competencies;
- general cultural competencies;
- educational and cognitive competencies;
- information competencies;
- communicative competencies: knowledge of languages, ways of interacting with other people, teamwork skills, knowledge of various social roles 4/10
- social and labor competencies;
- competence of personal self-improvement [10].

Ten key competencies of I.A. Zimnaya, united into three main groups.

I. Competencies related to a person as a person.

II. Competencies related to the social interaction of a person and the social sphere.

III. Competencies related to human activity:

- health-saving competencies;
- competencies of value-semantic orientation in the world;
- integration competencies: structuring of knowledge, increment of knowledge;
- competence of citizenship;
- self-improvement competencies, language and speech development.
- competencies of social interaction;
- competence in communication: oral and written, generation and acceptance of the text, knowledge and observance of etiquette, traditions;
- competence of cognitive activity: setting and solving cognitive tasks, intellectual activity of a person;
- competencies of activity: play, teaching, work, research activity;
- competencies of information technologies: reception processing, information delivery [11].

Despite the fact that there are many similarities in the classifications, scientists' opinions on the component composition of competencies differ. M. Kanal, D. Haimz, L.F. Bachman, I.A. Zimnaya, R.P. Milrud, I.R. Maksimova devoted their works to the issues of competence formation, I.L. Bim, A.K. Krupchenko, and other scientists. However, the problem of core competencies raises many questions today. The concretization of such concepts as "component composition of competencies", its detailed consideration, practical conclusions regarding the preparation of students in close connection with the acquired professional or profile competence, the reflection of this aspect in programs and didactic materials adequate to this learning goal, requires special study, and therefore should become the subject of

further scientific research. The topic of our research is "Formation of key competencies of profile-oriented English language teaching". English as a foreign language is studied at two VD schools: as a general education discipline (GE: General English) for those educational institutions, and for special purposes (ESP: English. Purposes) in vocational education institutions and professional activity courses.

Results Profile-oriented English language teaching is a new direction in the development of the theory and practice of teaching English for special purposes and a new direction of an appropriate approach to learning, which is based on the needs of students. Profile-oriented training is focused on specialization or the choice of a specialty in the following areas: science, technology, business, economics, social sciences, art. Any profile-oriented English language teaching is based on two types of goals: academic or professional "English language courses for academic purposes are designed to ensure the readiness of students to study a specialty in it." "Courses for professional purposes are designed to help working specialists learn to communicate in a language in a professional context, solve professionally significant tasks. The main difference between them is that in English language courses for academic purposes, more attention is paid to the formation of students' learning skills and skills that are the basis for continuing education, and courses for professional purposes are more pragmatic".

Discussion Main levers of specialized training are the implementation of the principles of differentiation and individualization. Profile differentiation of the content of education solves the problem of specialization of each person in a certain area at the level of general education provides for a conscious, voluntary choice by students of specialization of the content of education, cognitive needs, as well as the level achieved on the basis of knowledge and skills and professional intentions. Profile differentiation is closely related to- It is connected with the implementation of an individual approach in relation to each student in separate groups" [12]. The educational process, which is based on educational programs that differ in content and requirements for the student's level of knowledge. Let's clarify the structure of teaching a foreign language in the system of professional education and consider the purpose of training. Since the goal integrates all actions in the system and forms educational competencies.

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